

Survey 1 – Denmark

Questionnaire on the design of large continuous forest areas

In the questionnaire, we will first ask you to answer a number of questions about the last time you went on a walk in the forest. Next, we will ask about possible changes to large continuous forest areas.

Answer each question as best you can. There are no right or wrong answers, and some questions are easier to answer than others.

The questionnaire is easiest to read and complete on a computer or tablet/iPad. However, the questionnaire can also be completed on a mobile phone. It takes approx. 20-30 minutes to complete the form.

Remember to press "FINISH" after the last question - this will avoid us sending you a reminder.

I hereby consent to the data collected being used for research purposes - including publication in scientific journals and dissemination to the wider public. This also means that the results may potentially have an impact on future policy.

The results will be treated confidentially, and my answers will not be attributable to me by people outside the University of Copenhagen.

1. When was the last time you went for a walk in the forest?

(also short walks or, for example, very short walks are considered a "walk in the forest" if they were done entirely or partly with the purpose of getting to the forest - choose one answer)

- Today
- Less than 1 week ago
- 1 to 2 weeks ago
- 2 to 4 weeks ago
- 1 to 2 months ago
- 2 to 4 months ago
- 4 to 12 months ago
- More than 1 year ago

2a. What type of day was it?

(choose one answer)

- A weekday
- A Saturday or Sunday

2b. Were you on holiday when you visited the forest?

(choose one answer)

- Yes
- No

3a. Which forest did you visit?

(if you know/can remember the name of the forest, please write it here. If you do not know/can remember the name of the forest, please write "don't know")

3b. How far from your home is this forest?

(write approximate number of km.)

4. What did you do on that visit?

(select answer - more than one is welcome)

- Experienced nature
- Studied nature, watched birds, etc.
- Went for a walk
- Walked a dog
- Went running
- Exercised
- Cycling on a mountain bike
- Cycling (not mountain bike)
- Driving in a car
- Sat quietly and ate/grilled
- Collected berries, mushrooms, flowers, etc.
- Took photographs
- Went horseback riding
- Went hunting
- Went fishing
- Went on a hike with a nature guide/guide
- Spent the night in the forest
- Played, role-played, climbed trees, built caves, etc.
- Was at work
- Built a campfire
- Snow and/or ice activities
- Relaxed - did nothing/sunbathed
- Digital activities (was on social media, listened to music, geocaching, etc.)

- Was at work
- Other

5. How long did you spend on the actual trip to the forest?

(choose one answer)

- less than 2 minutes
- 2 to 5 minutes
- 5 to 10 minutes
- 10 minutes to 15 minutes
- 15 minutes to half an hour
- half an hour to 35 minutes
- 35 minutes to 1½ hours
- more than 1½ hours

6. How long did your visit to the forest last?

(choose one answer)

- less than 5 minutes
- 15 minutes
- 1/2 hour
- 1 hour
- a couple of hours
- 3 to 4 hours
- 5-8 hours
- more than 8 hours

Now follow a few more general questions about your forest visits.

7. Have you ever been on a trip to the forest where the main purpose was to...

(select answer - more than one is welcome)

- ...see the wild animals?
- ...see cows/horses that have been released to care for the forest/nature?
- ...go on a trip with a nature guide?
- ...sleep in a shelter?
- ...go hunting?
- ...walk the dog?
- ...go for a run?
- ...go for a ride?
- ...go mountain biking?
- ...relax/give my mind a break?
- ...go on a regular bike/gravel bike?
- None of these

8. How many times have you been on a trip to the forest during THE LAST 7 DAYS?

(even smaller trips or e.g. very short walks are considered a "trip in the forest", if they were done entirely or partly with the purpose of getting to the forest)

Write the number of times **in the last 7 days**:

9. How many times have you been on a trip in the forest during THE LAST YEAR (12 months)?

(even smaller trips or e.g. very short walks are considered a "trip in the forest", if they were done entirely or partly with the purpose of getting to the forest)

Write the number of times **in the last year (12 months)**:

10. How far is it from your place of residence to the NEAREST FOREST?

(write approximate number of km)

Large contiguous forest areas

Large, continuous forest areas can help to improve biodiversity. If you also introduce large grazing animals, biodiversity can be further improved. Introducing large grazing animals will also have an impact on how such forests are experienced by visitors. We are interested in knowing how this will affect your experience of visiting such forests.

In the following, we will describe some different forests and ask you to choose which, if any, you would like to visit. All of the forests are large forest areas of approximately 1,000 hectares.

Please only consider what this means for your forest visit – not what it means for biodiversity.

We will ask you a total of 6 questions. In each question, we ask you to choose whether you would visit one of the forests described in the near future.

If you would rather do something else, or would rather visit another forest, you can also choose “none of them”.

All forests vary in the following 8 points:

1. Age of the trees;
2. Whether the tree species are deciduous or coniferous;
3. Whether there are grazing animals;
4. Type of fence around the forest;
5. How many places you can access the forest through the fence;
6. Type of access point through the fence;
7. Whether you are allowed to bring your dog;
8. How far away the forest is from your starting point.

What the forest looks like

Forests can look different. The trees can be young or old. The tree species can be either deciduous or coniferous. If there are grazing animals, the forest will also typically become more open. The appearance of the forests will be shown with drawings like the example below. Note that the forest is shown in autumn mode.

Grazing animals

Various grazing animals have been introduced into forests around Denmark today. When grazing animals are introduced, the living conditions for other animals, plants and fungi are improved. This improves biodiversity in the area. Grazing also creates a more open forest. The species mentioned below will be present in the forests we describe in the upcoming questions. Some of the animals are shy, and you will therefore not necessarily see them on a forest visit. All animals will be monitored in accordance with the Animal Welfare Act.

b. Year-round grazing cattle, with horns

c. Year-round grazing cattle, without horns

d. Wild horse

e. Moose

f. European bison

g. Red deer

The type of fence around the forest

There will be a fence around the entire forest to prevent grazing animals from getting out of the forest. There will be no fence inside the forest.

The type of fence depends on the animals. Large wild animals such as red deer, elk and bison require a high fence. Other animals such as cattle, sheep and wild horses only need a low fence. However, there may still be forests with these animals that have a high fence around the entire forest. It may be that plans have been changed and other species have been introduced than originally planned.

How many places are there to access the forest through the fence:

1. Access through the outer fence by major forest roads
2. Access through the outer fence by major forest roads and by smaller footpaths

Types of access through the fence

You could get through the fence in the following ways:

Ladder

Cowgrate

Gate

Dog access

In some forests, dogs are not allowed. If dogs are allowed, they must always be on a leash. This is indicated by the following signs:

1. Dogs on a leash allowed
2. Dogs are not allowed

How far you have to travel to get to the forest

The forests we show you and ask you to choose from can be close or further away. We have shown how many kilometers away you should imagine the forest to be.

Remember that transportation takes time and costs money. Please consider that you could spend your time and money on something other than visiting the forest shown.

Choosing the forest you want to visit

We will now show you some different forests and ask you to choose the forest you could imagine visiting. The forests only vary in the conditions we have described here. That is, that they are completely similar in relation to, for example, how many other people there are, parking options or whether there is water nearby.

Presented forests may not currently exist in your area. However, we would like you to imagine that the forests are located at the described distance and that they are possible for you to visit.

If you do not want to visit any of the forests shown, but would rather do something else, select "None of them". For example, you may prefer to stay at home, visit another forest, or do something completely different.

1. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them.

	Skov 1	Skov 2	Ingen af dem
Afstand til skoven	10 KM	28 KM	
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov	Nåletræer	Nåletræer	
Forskelle i træernes alder	Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret	
Græssende dyr	Ingen græssende dyr		
Hegnets type	Intet hegn	Højt hegn	
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet	Ingen hegnbarriere for adgang		
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven	Ingen hegnbarriere for adgang	Adgang ved større skovveje	
Adgang for hunde	Hund i snor tilladt	Hunde ikke tilladt	

2. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them.

	Ingen af dem	Skov 1	Skov 2
Afstand til skoven		6 KM	6 KM
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov		Løvtræer	Nåletræer
Forskelle i træernes alder		Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret
Græssende dyr			Ingen græssende dyr
Hegnets type		Højt hegn	Intet hegn
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			Ingen hegnsbariere for adgang
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven		Adgang ved større skovveje	Ingen hegnsbariere for adgang
Adgang for hunde		Hund i snor tilladt	Hunde ikke tilladt

3. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them.

	Skov 1	Skov 2	Ingen af dem
Afstand til skoven	10 KM	1 KM	
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov	Løvtræer	Nåletræer	
Forskelle i træernes alder	Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret	
Græssende dyr			
Hegnets type	Lavt hegn	Højt hegn	
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven	Adgang ved større skovveje og ved mindre trampestier	Adgang ved større skovveje	
Adgang for hunde	Hund i snor tilladt	Hunde ikke tilladt	

4. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them.

	Skov 1	Skov 2	Ingen af dem
Afstand til skoven	10 KM	10 KM	
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov	Nåletræer	Løvtræer	
Forskelle i træernes alder	Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret	
Græssende dyr			
Hegnets type	Højt hegn	Lavt hegn	
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven	Adgang ved større skovveje og ved mindre trampestier	Adgang ved større skovveje	
Adgang for hunde	Hunde ikke tilladt	Hund i snor tilladt	

5. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them.

	Skov 1	Skov 2	Ingen af dem
Afstand til skoven	15 KM	21 KM	
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov	Løvtræer	Nåletræer	
Forskelle i træernes alder	Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret	
Græssende dyr			
Hegnets type	Lavt hegn	Højt hegn	
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven	Adgang ved større skovveje og ved mindre trampestier	Adgang ved større skovveje	
Adgang for hunde	Hunde ikke tilladt	Hund i snor tilladt	

6. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them

	Ingen af dem	Skov 1	Skov 2
Afstand til skoven		1 KM	21 KM
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov		Løvtræer	Nåletræer
Forskelle i træernes alder		Ens-aldret	Uens-aldret
Græssende dyr			
Hegnets type		Højt hegn	Lavt hegn
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven		Adgang ved større skovveje	Adgang ved større skovveje og ved mindre trampestier
Adgang for hunde		Hunde ikke tilladt	Hund i snor tilladt

7. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them

	Ingen af dem	Skov 1	Skov 2
Afstand til skoven		70 KM	15 KM
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov		Løvtræer	Løvtræer
Forskelle i træernes alder		Uens-aldret	Uens-aldret
Græssende dyr			Ingen græssende dyr
Hegnets type		Højt hegn	Intet hegn
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			Ingen hegnbarriere for adgang
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven		Adgang ved større skovveje	Ingen hegnbarriere for adgang
Adgang for hunde		Hund i snor tilladt	Hund i snor tilladt

8. Imagine that you are planning to take a walk in the forest in the near future. The following are possible forests that you could visit. Which one would you choose? You can also choose not to visit any of them

	Ingen af dem	Skov 1	Skov 2
Afstand til skoven		3 KM	1 KM
Hvordan skoven ser ud			
Typen af skov		Nåletræer	Løvtræer
Forskelle i træernes alder		Uens-aldret	Ens-aldret
Græssende dyr			
Hegnets type		Lavt hegn	Højt hegn
Typen af adgange gennem hegnet			
Hvor mange steder der er adgang gennem hegnet rundt om skoven		Adgang ved større skovveje og ved mindre trampestier	Adgang ved større skovveje
Adgang for hunde		Hunde ikke tilladt	Hund i snor tilladt

(Only shown to relevant respondents) In one or more of your answers you chose "None of them". Please indicate below which of these two options you had in mind when you made this choice:

- I wanted to visit a forest other than the two options.
- I wanted to do something other than go to the forest.

In the previous question we gave you the option to choose "none of them" instead of the forests indicated. What do you think this option meant?

- That I wanted to visit a forest other than the two options.
- That I wanted to do something other than go to the forest.

(Only shown to relevant respondents) In your last answer you indicated that you wanted to visit a forest other than the two options. What did you imagine this forest to be like?

Type of forest

- Broadleaf
- Coniferous
- Mixed

Differences in tree age

- Even-aged
- Uneven-aged

Distance to forest (km)

- Grazing animals
- No animals
- Sheep
- Year-round grazing cattle, with horns
- Year-round grazing cattle, without horns
- Wild horses
- Moose
- European bison
- Red deer
- Other animals

Type of fence

- No fence
- Low fence
- High fence

Type of access through the fence

- No fence
- Ladder
- Cowgrate
- Gate

How many places are there to access the forest through the fence

- No fence
- Access through the outer fence on major forest roads
- Access through the outer fence on major forest roads and on minor footpaths

Access for dogs

- Dogs allowed without a leash
- Dogs allowed on a leash
- Dogs not allowed

(Only shown to relevant respondents) What was the main reason why you did not choose any of the forests shown:

- They were too far away
- I prefer to visit the forest I usually visit
- I prefer to visit other natural areas
- I did not understand the questions
- The forests were different in many ways and it was easier not to go to either
- I do not want to visit a forest with grazing animals
- I do not want to visit a forest with a fence around it
- I prefer to do other things than walk in the forest
- I want to take my dog with me
- Other

(Only shown to relevant respondents) In the above question, you chose one of the forests shown each time. Why?

- The forests shown were all closer than the forests I otherwise have access to.
- I want to visit a forest with grazing animals, and I do not have access to any other forests that have it.
- I want to go to the forest. And those were the two options to choose from.
- It was easier to choose one of the forests than to choose “none of them”.
- I felt that I should choose one of the forests shown.
- There was always one of the forests shown that I would rather visit than do other things.
- I forgot that I could choose “none of them”.
- Other

12. Visiting one of the forests shown involved traveling a distance. How much weight did you place on the distance to travel in your choices?

- I didn't consider it at all
- A little
- Some

- A lot
- It was the most important

13. How likely or unlikely do you think it is that you will see the grazing animals if you visit a forest like the one described?

	Sheep	Cattle with horns	Wild horses	European bison	Red deer	Cattle without horns	Moose
Very unlikely							
Unlikely							
Neither							
Likely							
Very likely							
Don't know							

14. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about your choices of animals in the previous paragraph:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly agree	Don't know
I am afraid that some animals may harm me or others around me.						
I think that I will have a better chance of seeing the animals, which is something I would like to do.						
I attribute a cultural value to the fact that the						

animals are there.						
I believe that animals will survive better in nature in Denmark.						
I believe that some of the animals may be endangered and want their population to increase.						
I believe that animals can have better living conditions in nature if they are in large, connected natural areas.						
I believe that this will increase biodiversity in forests with endangered animals.						
I prefer that non-domestic animals are present in the forest rather than domestic animals.						

The next few questions are about NATURAL NATIONAL PARKS.

The purpose of the nature national parks is to contribute to strengthening nature and biodiversity, i.e. the richness of species. It is planned that a total of 18 nature national parks will be designated in Denmark.

The nature national parks will be of different sizes, but they are larger, continuous areas of typically approximately 10 square kilometers or more, which are surrounded by fences up to 2.5 meters high. There will be general public access to these areas through gates, paths or walkways.

The nature national parks are kept free from forestry and agricultural production, and large grazing animals such as cattle, horses or deer are released, which will help develop the nature in the areas and provide better living conditions for a number of animal, plant and fungal species and thus improve the biodiversity in these areas. The animals that are released must find their own food. In the case of some of the animals, they will have the opportunity to reproduce themselves. Supervision of the animals is carried out in accordance with the Animal Welfare Act.

15. How interested would you be in visiting a national park?

- Not interested
- A little interested
- Somewhat interested
- Very interested
- Don't know

16. Think about one of the larger natural areas that you often visit. Do you think you would visit that natural area more or less if it became a national park?

- I would visit the area more
- I would visit the area as before
- I would visit the area less
- I would stop visiting the area altogether
- Never visit a larger natural area
- Don't know

17. What is your overall attitude towards nature national parks?

- Very negative
- Negative
- Neither or
- Positive
- Very positive
- Don't know

18. It is being considered what kind of animals should be released into the national parks. To what extent are you negative or positive about the following animals being released?

	Very negative	Negative	Neither	Positive	Very positive	Don't know
Typical domestic animals (e.g. sheep, goats, cattle and horses)						
Animals that are wild in parts of Denmark (e.g. red deer and wild boar)						
Animals that are not wild in Denmark (e.g. moose and bison)						

19. Have you previously walked or cycled in a natural area with larger grazing animals (in larger enclosures with public access)?

- Yes – within the past year (12 months)
- Yes – but it was more than a year ago
- No – never

20. Do you have experience handling/caring for larger animals, such as horses and cows?

- Yes – a lot of experience
- Yes – a little experience
- No – no experience

21. How would you describe your knowledge of “rewilding”?

- I don't know what rewilding means.
- I know a little about rewilding.
- I have a general knowledge of rewilding.
- I know more than most people about rewilding.
- I know a lot about rewilding.

22. What is your stance on rewilding?

- I don't know what rewilding means
- Very negative. I'm very against it.
- Negative. I'm against it.
- Neither/nor
- Positive. I'm positive about it.
- Very positive. I'm very positive about it.
- I haven't decided.

Finally, we would like to ask for some information about yourself.

23a. Please state your gender

- Male
- Female
- Other

23b. What is your age?

24. How would you best describe your current family situation?

(choose one answer)

- Young, living at home
- Single – no children
- Couple – no children
- Family/single with one or more children/part-time children under 5 years old living at home
- Family/single with children/part-time children all 5 years old or older living at home
- Couple/single without children/part-time children living at home (moved away from home) and not yet retired/retired
- Retired/recipient of early retirement, etc.
- Other
- Do not wish to provide information

25. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

(choose one answer)

- Primary school (public school, private school, middle school, junior high school)
- Secondary education (including HF, HH, HTX, etc. and student course)
- Vocational education (e.g. business school, technical school)
- Short higher education (1-2½ years, e.g. laboratory technician, computer scientist)
- Medium higher education (2½-4 years, e.g. professional bachelor, nurse, school teacher)
- Long higher education (university education, bachelor, master, PhD)
- Other
- Do not wish to provide information

26. What is your current occupation?

(choose one answer)

- Self-employed
- Employed spouse
- Full-time employee (at least 32 hours)
- Part-time/reduced-time employee
- Unemployed
- On leave
- In training
- Early retirement pensioner
- National pensioner
- Early retirement pensioner
- Other
- Does not wish to provide information

27. Are you...

(select each answer option that applies to you)

- ...Horse rider?
- ...Hunter?
- ...Angling?
- ...Runner?
- ...Cyclist
- ...Mountain biker?
- ...Ornithologist/botanist?
- ...Mushroom picker?
- I do not belong to any of these groups

28. Which of the following associations/organizations are you a member of?

(select each association you are a member of)

- Danish Nature Conservation Association
- WWF (World Wildlife Fund)
- Verdens Skove/Nepenthes
- Danish Ornithological Association
- Hunting Association

- Angling Association
- Scouts
- Orientation Club (O-løb)
- Running/Athletics Club
- Cycling/Mountain Bike Club
- Other associations/organizations with activities/interest in the forest/nature
- I am NOT a member of any of these associations

If OTHER associations, please write which ones here:

29. What size city do you live in?

(choose one answer)

- In the countryside / in a village (under 500 inhabitants)
- In a small town (under 10,000 inhabitants)
- In a larger city (over 10,000 inhabitants)
- In the capital area

30. Does your household have a...

(Choose each answer option that applies to your household)

- ...Car?
- ...Boat?
- ...Electric bicycle?
- ...Allotment garden?
- ...Garden?
- ...Holiday home/summer house?
- ...Horse?
- ...Dog?
- NONE of these

31. What is your household's total annual income before tax?

(choose one answer)

- Under 100,000 DKK
- 100,000 – 199,999 DKK
- 200,000 – 299,999 DKK
- 300,000 – 399,999 DKK
- 400,000 – 499,999 DKK
- 500,000 – 599,999 DKK
- 600,000 – 699,999 DKK
- 700,000 – 799,999 DKK
- 800,000 – 899,999 DKK
- 900,000 – 999,999 DKK
- 1,000,000 – 1,099,999 DKK
- 1,100,000 – 1,199,999 DKK
- 1,200,000 – 1,299,999 DKK
- 1,300,000 – 1,399,999 DKK
- 1,400,000 – 1,499,999 DKK
- 1,500,000 DKK or more
- Don't know / don't want to say

If you have any comments or suggestions, please write them here:

THANK YOU FOR YOUR HELP

Your answers have now been saved. End the survey by clicking "END"